

Additional Activity Reporting

Partnership

EOSC: European Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud

Total Amount per Partnership

321844688

Additional Activity category

1. Support to additional R&I

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers:

- a) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded and executed by private partners in the association;
- b) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded by a public research funder (which is a partner in the association, or not) and executed by private partners in the association (n.b. regional or national programmes to support R&I are often offered by public funders).
- c) Additional (i.e. not receiving/having received EU funding) R&I funded by a public research funder which is a partner in the association through for instance a regional or national R&I funding programme.

For case b) above, please note that:

- If a private partner has received co-funding for a project from a public entity which is NOT a partner in the association, then only the part financed by the private partner should be counted in this category (but not the part co-financed by the public entity).

For case c) above, please note that:

- If a private partner has received co-funding for a project from a public entity which IS a partner in the association, then the entire project should be counted in this category (also the part co-financed by the public entity).

R&I should be understood as covering the full range of TRL levels.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

119 063 890 €

Additional Activity Number

1.1

Additional Activity Name

Upgrade of existing research infrastructures

Additional Activity type

Upgrade of existing research infrastructures and e-infrastructure so that they may be federated through EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

1. Upgrade of the existing institutional and national repositories (e.g., integration of ORCID, assigning DOIs), upgrade of the data catalogues
2. Upgrade of the existing institutional, local, and national data/ research infrastructures (e.g., databases, publishing platforms, e-archives) that may be federated through EOSC
3. Implementation of interfaces to integrate computer and data management solutions to ease access and reuse data
4. Scale up the e-infrastructure capabilities of data centres and improving their connectivity with the EOSC and other European infrastructures
5. Upgrade of data storage infrastructures and/ or research data management services (e.g., upgrade of DOI management application)
6. Enhancement of DMP online tools
7. Upgrade of the Digital Object Gateway
8. Upgrade of the SSH Open Marketplace
9. Integration of FAIR-Data services into existing infrastructures, archives, repositories
10. Integration of a new data processing centre in the EOSC portal, offering Cloud resources to EU researchers and

upgrade of existing scientific cloud providers in the EOSC portal

11. Provision of a Belnet Service desk for Open Sciences related tools (OS related tools: DMPOnline, Belnet FTP, Filesender, Orfeo, AAI, LTDP) and a Belnet Portal for Open Sciences related tools (OS related tools: DMPOnline, Belnet FTP, Filesender, Orfeo, AAI, LTDP)

12. Provision of funds for the upgrade of national centre of expertise in the social sciences and national data & service center for the humanities which can be federated to EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research

SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design

SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge

SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges

SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

OO2- Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)

OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024

OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

OO13- Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

91 079 342 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Agora storage: Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

Success story description

Agora storage: first upgrade of disk capacity (to be completed in the following years), for management, processing and exploitation of scientific data and research results, MEEP project: flexible emulation platform for Exascale Supercomputers and others, based on European-developed IP (co-financed).

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://meep-project.eu/>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

openRDM.eu: Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich

Success story description

OpenRDM.eu offers a research data management service to the international research community, focused on active data management. Active research data management (ARDM) is the process of organising data during an ongoing research project (data annotation, storage and backup). The service is based around the ARDM platform openBIS, developed for the last 12 years by the Scientific IT Services of Informatikdienste (ID SIS) at ETH Zurich. OpenBIS is a server-client application: the remote server hosts the database and storage backends which are accessed by the users from their local machines via a web browser. OpenBIS combines a data management

platform with a digital lab notebook and a sample and protocol management system.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Research Institutes
- Public at large
- Academia
- Public Authorities
- Other

Website

<https://openbis.ch/index.php/openrdm-eu/>

Success story number

3

Success Story Name

National Financing Initiative for Research Infrastructure: The Research Council of Norway

Success story description

The National Financing Initiative for Research Infrastructure at the Research Council seeks to build up relevant, up-to-date infrastructure that is accessible to the Norwegian research community, trade and industry. Contributions included are only for upgrade of relevant, existing RIs and e-infrastructure that may be federated through EOSC.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Research Institutes
- Public at large
- Academia
- Public Authorities
- Other

Website

<https://www.forskningsradet.no/en/apply-for-funding/funding-from-the-research-council/infrastruktur/>

Success story number

4

Success Story Name

Open Research Knowledge Graph: TIB Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology

Success story description

TIB developed the Open Research Knowledge Graph comprehensively for describing, representing and analysing research contributions comparatively along research questions. The ORKG has meanwhile 1,000 users and comprises more than 10,000 description in 500 fields of science. The ORKG was integrated into the EOSC and works on various smaller aspects to further deepen and broaden this integration.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Research Institutes
- Public at large
- Academia
- Public Authorities
- Other

Website

<https://orkg.org>

Additional Activity Number

1.2

Additional Activity Name

Development and deployment of EOSC-compatible search engines

Additional Activity type

1.2 Development and deployment of EOSC-compatible search engines to allow the researchers to explore rich metadata and semantic descriptions in EOSC-connected registers

Description of Additional Activity

1. Development of terminology services for exploring, publishing, and developing shared ontologies, vocabularies, and terminologies
2. Implementation of data catalogues together with an automatic metadata enrichment
3. Development of research output discovery in e.g. Limo Lirias, Research Data Repository front-end, metadata distribution to FRIS portal, OpenAire, Google Scholar and Google Dataset Search
4. Deployment of EOSC-compatible metadata repositories and semantic interoperability tools
5. Integration of existing data repositories with organisational services for metadata indexing
6. Development of online platform to reduce the barriers for accessing scientific publications by citizens
7. Establishment of the EOSC-compatible search portal that constitutes a single-entry point for searching, discovery and recall of thousands of scientific and scholarly publications, distributed by several repositories
8. Integration of metadata search engine and platform for FAIR epidemiological computational modelling and simulation
9. Preparation of platforms for academic libraries, including search engine for both documents and data from one access point
10. Deployment and integration of open research knowledge graphs for semantically describing research contributions
11. Development of the comprehensive, EOSC-compatible Information System for acquiring, processing, preservation and provision research and bibliometric information and publications
12. Deployment of the FAIR metadata catalogues, vocabularies, services

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO2- Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
OO13- Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

7 460 910 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Biodataverse: National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS)

Success story description

The BioDataVerse will be developed on a base unit of 1PB replicated storage initially, This base will be designed with a goal of scalability in order to answer progressively INSB (National Infrastructure in life sciences) needs.

The centre Mersenne is a diamond open access scientific publishing infrastructure developed by Mathdoc, a support and research unit of the CNRS and the Université Grenoble Alpes. The centre Mersenne provides all the publishing tools and services that enable editorial teams to manage, produce and disseminate their publications.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://www.centre-mersenne.org/>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

e-Varamu: University of Tartu

Success story description

Estonian e-Repository and Conservation of Collections- E-repository e-Varamu ensures the availability of information resources preserved and created in Estonian research and heritage institutions, which are necessary for R&D and creative activities. Three services are being developed: the digitalization and physical conservation of collections and making information available in the E-repository portal. The final goal of the project is to develop FULL collection of research and cultural heritage collection which includes resources from all Estonian research and heritage institutions.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other

Website

<https://www.e-varamu.ee/>

large

Additional Activity Number **Additional Activity Name**
1.3 Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR

Additional Activity type

Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR (e.g. the deployment of online tools for data FAIRification or to help creating FAIR Data Management Plans)

Description of Additional Activity

1. Development and pilot of public data repository services for institutions not having capacity to deploy their own repository
2. Provision of standard services for Data Management Plan Tools (e.g., DMPOnline), implementation of DMP standards, deployment of different FAIR online tools to support researchers e.g., DMP tools, PRET platform, iRODS infrastructure for active data management, diversified storage solutions, tools like FAIR-Aware, FAIR EVA online assessment tool
3. Integration of online DMP tools with organisational tools such as repositories and data registers
4. Implementation of the machine-actionable DMP tools, development of the DAMAP tool, an open-source software facilitating the creation of DMPs
5. Integration of local CRIS systems with DMP tool
6. Development of DMPonline Metadata for Machines toolbox for ontologies and metadata definition
7. Collaboration on FAIR DMPs, collaboration on Data Stewardship Wizard deployment
8. Enhancement of existing UIs for data access in correspondence with EOSC requirements for FAIR data
9. Deployment of Domain Data Protocols and F-UJI FAIR assessment tools
10. Contribution to various FAIR-related activities, such as the Leibniz Data Manager as a open-source FAIR data repository, the TIB Terminology Service for the collaborative creation and publishing of FAIR research data ontologies or the ORKG which allows to FAIRify research data currently hidden in PDF publications
11. Deployment of management platforms for metadata quality
12. Implementation of the FAIR Checker - a tool to assess the FAIR metrics of a resource
13. Implementation of the revised manual of data management which includes online tool for FAIR assessment
14. The Smart Guidance tool for the FAIRification of rare disease registries
15. Development of the data repository service allowing the publication of large-scale datasets to support researchers to make large data sets FAIR and discoverable within EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
- OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

7 824 438 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

FAIR tools to support researchers: Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

Success story description

Development, hosting, maintenance and support for different FAIR tools to support the KU Leuven researchers in every step of the life cycle: a.o. DMP tool, PRET platform (PRivacy and ETHics review tool). iRODS infrastructure for active data management, diversified storage solutions (sensitive, big, support of multiple protocols, mirrored). Globus for efficient data transfer and access during research, KU Leuven Research Data Repository for FAIR data publication.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
- Research Institutes Public Authorities

Website

<https://www.kuleuven.be/rdm/en/tools>

Public at large Other

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Smart Guidance tool for FAIRification: Sofia University "St.Kliment Ohridski"

Success story description

The Smart Guidance tool for the FAIRification of rare disease registries was released on the 18th of July. This is a questionnaire-based tool built on the Data Stewardship Wizard that will guide users (e.g. data stewards) through the process of making their registry more FAIR. It covers various aspects like the composition of the FAIRification team, best practices for data representation, and giving access to your data. Bulgaria is a member of the EJP RD project that developed the EJP RD Smart Guidance Knowledge Model.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://erica-rd.eu/the-smart-guidance-tool-for-the-fairification-of-rare-disease-registries/>

Additional Activity Number

1.4

Additional Activity Name

Development and publication of large scale studies

Additional Activity type

Development and publication of large scale studies

Description of Additional Activity

- 1.Funding of two large open cohort studies: the Swiss Transplant and the HIV Cohort Study aiming at a nationwide comprehensive and structured data collection and build a national, open database
- 2.Supporting and hosting several large studies like LCBC, Norment, Elixir (NFEGA) , Astrophysics where data is collected, generated and eventually supposed to become FAIR
- 3.Population study on opening research data at Polish universities and science units
- 4.A sociological-economic-technological audit of the national library ecosystem

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO2- Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

8 829 000 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Translations and Open Science project: Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for the Social Sciences and Humanities

Success story description

Translations and Open Science project (funded by the French Ministry of Higher education and Research) to coordinate a series of preparatory studies on: a) Mapping and collection of corpora of bilingual scientific texts which will serve as training dataset for specialised translation engines, source data for terminology extraction, and translation memory creation; b) Use cases, drafting an overview of the current translation practices in scholarly communication to define a technology-based scientific translation service (associated features, expected quality, editorial and technical workflows, and involved human experts); c) Machine translation output evaluation, evaluating the output of a set of translation engines with specialised texts and d) budget projections to develop and run the service.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://operas.hypotheses.org/5630>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

HEP data intensive programs: Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN)

Success story description

INFN is part of HEP data intensive programs, such as the LHC experiments, Virgo, Belle-II, DUNE experiments and many others, which analyze datasets at the Exabyte level by using a shared, distributed computing infrastructure. The output of these large-scale are journal publications, software and computing tools, and experimental datasets. The FAIRness of these results and their adherence to Open Science principles, and thus to EOSC, are under discussion within the national and international HEP communities,

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://home.infn.it/en/csn5-technological-research-experiments>

Additional Activity Number

1.5

Additional Activity Name

Contribution to operating core functions of a Minimum Viable EOSC ecosystem

Additional Activity type

Contribution to operating core functions of a Minimum Viable EOSC ecosystem

Description of Additional Activity

1. AAI infrastructure deployment
2. Implementation of MVE Research Infrastructures (e.g. Connectome Research Infrastructure)
3. Preparation of the secure cloud environment and contribution to the deployment of country-wide AAI fully compliant with EOSC architecture (also providing fully compliant LS AAI for the Life Science community Europe-wide)
4. Cloud operation and management of the EOSC compliant AAI infrastructure
5. Maintenance of BSC AAI federation in platforms like ELIXIR and B2ACCES, maintenance of the BSC provider profile on the EOSC Portal
6. Coordination of national AAI federation - AAI@EduHR
7. Implementation of the EOSC AAI within EuroHPC
8. Development of services for the EOSC, including AAI services, Orchestration, Cloud integration
9. Implementation and deployment of federated tools for the operations of distributed cloud infrastructures

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO6- Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by

2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

3 870 200 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

National Repository Platform for Research Data: Masaryk University

Success story description

Cloud and kubernetes provisioning for the data analysis; development and management of the EOSC compliant AAI infrastructure. This in our case overlaps with Action 1,1, so the split between Actions 1.1, and Action 1.5 is rather artificial (but the sum holds) and is supported through the e-INFRA CZ in 2023 to be replaced by the National Repository Platform for Research Data project funding in 2024.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.eosc.cz/en/about-eosc-cz/national-support/national-repository-platform>

Additional Activity category

2. Scale-up of technologies

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers different scale-up activities (typically at TRL levels 4-5) . These are mostly trials/tests of proof of concept models, i.e. validation of the technology in lab or relevant environment. These activities must be totally funded and executed by private partners only. If there is public co-funding, they should be reported in Category 1.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

12 465 822 €

Additional Activity Number

2.1

Additional Activity Name

Investment done complementing the results of a project, bringing it to a higher TRL level or deployment

Additional Activity type

Investment done complementing the results of a project, bringing it to a higher TRL level (e.g. EOSC thematic services) or to deployment

Description of Additional Activity

- 1.Continuous improvement of thematic services registered in EOSC Portal (e.g. support on the development of EOSC thematic services)
- 2.Various investments within Connectome porject as well as investments being part of ELIXIR, LifeWatch and and HL-LHC

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO2-Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing

societal challenges

SO8- Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025

OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

257 655 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Strategic Working Plan: e-Science and Technology European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research

Success story description

Strategic Working Plan

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

Additional Activity Number

2.2

Additional Activity Name

Uptake of EOSC projects' outcomes

Additional Activity type

Uptake of EOSC projects' outcomes through adoption of, for instance, new open specifications, standards for data interoperability, common EOSC frameworks for managing AAI, also but not exclusively in the context of public procurements

Description of Additional Activity

1. Integrator of new or updated services resulting from EOSC-related projects in the VLO and make them discoverable through EOSC Portal within the SSH Open Marketplace
2. Adoption of open (I)VOA standards for interoperability
3. Adoption of outcomes of relevant projects (e.g. SSHOC, EOSC Future, OpenAIRE, OPERAS)
4. Injection of knowledge from 'EOSC interoperability framework' and 'A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)' and AAI architecture into national working groups and upcoming projects
5. Uptake of the Bio-Image Analysis Desktop (BAND) service from EOSC-Life in 2023 to add the Life Science login
6. Implementation of data management and data analysis services for multiple research domains using common technology (resulting from the ESCAPE project) such as Data Lake
7. FBI data roadmap for 2022-2023: using the EOSC standards and AAI for biological image management

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO5- Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata

frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
 OO6- Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
 OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
 OO12- Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

6 272 155 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Implementation of data management and analysis services: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas

Success story description

Implementation of data management and data analysis services for multiple research domains using common technology to profit from economies of scale. These common technologies are for example some of the ones resulting from the ESCAPE project (2019-2022) such as the Data Lake.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://projectescape.eu/news/escape-dios-development-and-application-automatic-workflow-replication-scientific-data>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Bio-Image Analysis Desktop: European Molecular Biology Laboratory

Success story description

Takeover of the Bio-Image Analysis Desktop (BAND) service from EOSC-Life in 2023. Adding the Life Science login, update software and/or add new one, do a bit of user management, and implement collection of user statistics.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://band.embl.de/#/eosc-landingpage>

Additional Activity Number

2.3

Additional Activity Name

Implementation of technical specifications required to provide services through the EOSC

Additional Activity type

Implementation of technical specifications required to provide services through the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

1. Standardization and vocabulary development activities relevant for EOSC
2. Implementation of state-of-the-art standards for metadata, interoperability and persistent identification for the upgrading of the cultural heritage digitised collections repository
3. Support implementation of technical specifications within AUSSDA/CESSDA catalogue with link to EOSC
4. Implementation of technical specifications required to provide repository and LTP services through the EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1- Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4- Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO5- The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
SO7- EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1- Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO6- Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
OO10- Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024
OO11- Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025
OO12- Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

5 936 012 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

AMSHIstorica: Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna

Success story description

Implementation of state of the art standards for metadata, interoperability and persistent identification for the upgrading of the cultural heritage digitised collections repository (AMSHIstorica),

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://amshistorica.unibo.it/>

Additional Activity category

3. Demonstrators

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers demonstrations of a prototype. These demonstration activities would typically be at TRL levels 6-8. These activities must be totally funded and executed by private partners only. If there is public-co-funding, they should be reported in Category 1.

Additional activity reported under this category

Yes
 No

Amount per category

51 020 642 €

Additional Activity Number

3.1

Additional Activity Name

Investment in platforms and pilots supporting EOSC and sharing FAIR, open data.

Additional Activity type

Investment in new platforms, demonstrators, pilot use cases exploiting domain-specific user environments and supporting the EOSC vision including the value of sharing FAIR and open research data and other research digital objects such as software

Description of Additional Activity

- 1.Pilot of new services and pilot applications in the context of the Open Research Knowledge Graph for various applications and science domains
- 2.Implementation of a pilot case for digital critical national editions, fully compliant with state-of-the-art domain standards and EOSC vision for FAIR data
- 3.Development of the AlmaHealthDB (AHDB) infrastructure that allows researchers to collect and access large volumes of health data in compliance with legal, organizational, and regulatory requirements. AHDB adopts a FAIR by design approach, and develops a shared infrastructure for ensuring the highest interoperability level, better control, and better cost-effectiveness, especially for multi-center studies.
- 4.Develop and prototype a data access and analysis platform for multimessenger astronomy
- 5.Develop and prototype a data analysis and preservation service for material science data
- 6.Build up relevant, up-to-date infrastructure that is accessible to the national research community, trade and industry that may be federated through EOSC
- 7.Build technical prototypes in EOSC-compatible frameworks, showcase them and work with end-users
- 8.Set up a controlled vocabulary registry as a demonstrator for a federated registry service infrastructure
- 9.Development and implementation of standards and data interfaces for research information
- 10.Establishment of new data centers (e.g., national Ocean Data Center)
- 11.Development of a pilot data long-tale repository, development of InvenioRDM-based repository for research data and open education resources
- 12.ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) works to develop a sustainable research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands. Through ODISSEI, researchers within the social sciences have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections
- 13.Development of a national sustainable research infrastructure for the social sciences where researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO7 EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
- OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
- OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
- OO10 Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

44 749 379 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

CARDS (Czech Academic and Research Discovery Services): National Library of Technology

Success story description

Metadata standard recommendation should be defined and repositories created on the National repository platform and indexed to the National metadata catalogue should follow this standard recommendations, Metadata WG based with project EOSC-CZ will help with definition and also dissemination to subject repositories. This is a part of the national project CARDS financed from the structural funds of the EU.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
- Research Institutes Public Authorities
- Public at large Other

Website

<https://cards.techlib.cz/>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Links between RIs and EOSC: European Organization for Nuclear Research

Success story description

CERN is working to establish links between its research infrastructures (LHC now and High luminosity LHC in the future) and EOSC. CERN is also building a new data centre which will be ready for for usage in 2024. These activities contribute to CERN's open science engagement.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://cds.cern.ch/record/2735179>

Additional Activity Number

3.2

Additional Activity Name

(Pre-)commercial services and capabilities

Additional Activity type

New (pre-)commercial services and capabilities along the data life cycle addressing current and anticipated needs of the research community at large

Description of Additional Activity

1. Implementation of services and related policies for data management, processing and orchestration in accordance with potential commercial use-cases
2. Implementation of a set of additional commercial functionalities to the Educloud that aims to serve as general service available for users to be consumed from anywhere
3. Development of commercial services and capabilities under Connectome project
4. Development of sustainable OA Book focused analytics service, helping safeguard and support diversity in the voices, perspectives, geographies, topics and languages made visible through OA Books, to be Findable and Accessible in EOSC

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO7 EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
 OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
 OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
 OO10 Deploy and operate an authentication and OO10 authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

6 271 263 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

ORD Programme: Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich

Success story description

ORD Programme ETH Domain ELN-Project: Gatekeeper – a comprehensive approach to connect data sources across the ETH Domain API-Projects submitted to Programme Steering Committee in 2023

The open sharing of research data is essential for progress and excellence in all scientific fields and research disciplines. ORD makes research results transparent and more robust by enabling the re-use of data. It facilitates research collaboration across disciplines and institutions, fostering creativity and innovation. The ability to see and understand what research is doing is of great value to society and is becoming a vital resource in addressing

global challenges.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

https://open-research-data-portal.ch

Additional Activity category

4. Creating new business opportunities

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities which aim at turning a fully developed and functional innovation into a business opportunity. It concerns activities such as investing in start-ups, spin-offs, incubators, accelerators etc. that will take forward the solutions/products developed within the partnership's projects. Please note that "Creating business opportunities" can only happen once the product or service is available in its fully developed form (i.e. when the "Scale-up of technologies" step is fully finished, and normally also when the "Demonstrators" step has been finished).

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

765 000 €

Additional Activity Number

4.1

Additional Activity Name

Invest in start-ups and spin-offs

Additional Activity type

Invest in start-ups, spin-offs on solutions developed within the projects

Description of Additional Activity

1. Support the exploitation of project results through the initiation of dedicated spin-offs such as LIBRIS-tech (e-publishing), InnoÉtics (communication, robotics and knowledge processing), SymbioLabs (machine learning digital services)
2. Invest in "Foodcapture"- a spin-off from TSD looking at nutrition surveillance in homes for elderly people and in hospitals

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

513 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Support the exploitation of project results: Athena - Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies

Success story description

Support the exploitation of project results through the initiation of dedicated spin-offs and development of business plans - The "Athena" RC executives and researchers based on the robust applied research served and its stable industrial orientation, operate from the beginning with a strong entrepreneurial spirit which led to creation of spin-offs companies where promising scientific results meet to date the needs of society and industry. These companies follow their own path and create the opportunities for the new generation of younger pioneers

to make up prospective and powerful technological proposals.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.athenarc.gr/el/entrepreneurship>

Additional Activity Number

4.2

Additional Activity Name

Start incubators/accelerators

Additional Activity type

Start incubators/accelerators

Description of Additional Activity

1. Organisation of bootcamps, hackathons and datathons within Corallia project/ Hellenic Technology Cluster Initiative that fosters collaboration between Science, Entrepreneurship and Industry, also in terms of data accessibility

"

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

66 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Additional Activity Number

4.3

Additional Activity Name

Matchmaking between different start-ups

Additional Activity type

Matchmaking between different start-ups, - SMEs, participating companies, stakeholders

Description of Additional Activity

1. Support for SMEs and start-ups through Veksthuset and Dscience (Centre for Computational and Data Science) centres by e.g. organising events/ exchanges related to data/ information sharing

2. Matchmaking activities within Big Data and Business Analytics Observatory that aims to understand and portray the status quo of FAIR Data & Analytics in Italy. The Data Center workgroup is established for research related to activities on the Cloud Transformation Observatory with the aim of creating and spreading knowledge on the Italian Data Center supply chain and on the infrastructure existing on the Italian territory.

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

186 000 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Big Data and Business Analytics Observatory: Politecnico di Milano

Success story description

Big Data and Business Analytics Observatory aims to understand and portray the status quo of FAIR Data & Analytics in Italy. The Data Center workgroup is established for research related to activities on the Cloud Transformation Observatory with the aim of creating and spreading knowledge on the Italian Data Center supply chain and on the infrastructure existing on the Italian territory. It is a strategic asset for the digitalization of the Country and a key element of international competitiveness.

The Data Center infrastructure aims to be a technological enabler for the delivery of services and solutions supporting digitalization of businesses and of the business models of the country's digital supply chain. In the past years the market has shown growing interest, resulting in a considerable increase of investments and the opening of new Data Center infrastructure on the Italian territory.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
- Research Institutes Public Authorities
- Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.osservatori.net/en/research/active-observatories/data-center>

Additional Activity Number

4.4

Additional Activity Name

Procurement of innovative platform for scientific data preservation and management

Additional Activity type

Procurement of innovative platform for scientific data preservation and management

Description of Additional Activity

Procurement of innovative platform for scientific data preservation and management

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
- OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

0 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Additional Activity category

5. Training and skills development

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category covers activities that aim to identify and perform the skills and training programmes needed for the workforce that will produce and/or use the new product/service.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
- No

Amount per category

25 573 992 €

Additional Activity Number

5.1

Additional Activity Name

Education, training and skills development

Additional Activity type

Addressing the development of education, training and skills development in Open science and FAIR data management of research artefacts. Coordinating and aligning relevant curricula on skills for FAIR and Open Science, and training frameworks for young researchers, civil servants and policy makers

Description of Additional Activity

1. Diverse education, training, and skills development activities (webinars, workshops, online courses, mutual learning events) in Open Science, RDM and FAIR data management of research artefacts also in the context of EOSC related services
2. Contribution to the National Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition by supporting RPOs in delivering training on FAIR & ORDM as well as on the use of EOSC-relevant services
3. Development of training materials and guidelines covering RDM topics like anonymization, best practices, FAIR principles, DMPs; continuous upgrading of training materials on FAIR data, RDM, DMP, OA
4. Data stewardship-oriented activities: data stewards' recruitment campaigns, development of data stewardship curriculums, establishment of data steward training programmes, data stewardship certificate courses
5. Training activities provided by RDM and OS support desks, support to RPOs in delivering training on FAIR and RDM
6. Development of training resources about Open Science and FAIR data for the arts and humanities research communities
7. Development of the SSH Training Toolkit that provides a FAIR overview of teaching instruments with a focus on language data
8. Advisory services, courses and OS trainings for students, PhD candidates, university authorities, administrative staff, librarians, policy makers
9. Training activities focusing on experts (train-the-trainers), researchers (data producers and data users), grant holders
10. Diploma for 'scientific data management', certifications in OS
11. Build capacities to sustain learning corpora for digital skills and tools so that EOSC represents a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub
12. Cycle of conferences and annual events to promote scientific careers, incorporating aspects related to open science, FAIR data management plans
13. Training platforms with courses on Open Access publishing and FAIR data /RDM
14. Wide range of OS and RDM activities within the dedicated Centers e.g., Open Science Competence Centre, Knowledge Research Education Centre, Digital Scholarship Centre

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

25 573 992 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Open access and data management trainings: National Science Centre Poland

Success story description

Open access and data management trainings for NCN grant applicants, NCN grant holders, data stewards, researchers and PhD students: 1) MOOC (ang, Massive Open Online Courses) - Research data management for data stewards (basic and intermediate level) - Training in developing the knowledge and competence of researchers in the area of research data management (basic and intermediate level) 2) Disciplinary trainings on research data management for: - linguistics - earth sciences - social communication sciences and media - sociology - medical, pharmaceutical and health sciences 3) Webinars on NCN's Policy on Open Access to Publications 4) Webinars on Data Management Plans in research proposals submitted to NCN

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://www.ncn.gov.pl/en/aktualnosci/2024-01-18-szkolenia-dla-wnioskodawcow-2024>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Open Science training and support of digital skills: Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information

Success story description

Providing Open Science training and support of digital skills. Support of next-generation of data/EOSC professionals through trainings and educational activities with aim to meet the demands of open science and open data best practices. Development of a leadership programme to foster the right policy environment that supports digital skills and trainings. Building of capacities for digital skills and tools in order EOSC may represent a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://otvorenaveda.cvtisr.sk/>

Success story number

3

Success Story Name

Open Science Knowledge Hub: Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea / Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii

Success story description

Having a main role in facilitating capacity building for OS, as the Open Science Knowledge Hub and as co-coordinator of the Romanian OS Cloud Initiative (RO-NOSCI), (trainings/ course support actions, mutual learning events for researchers, civil servants and policy makers)

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/ro-nosci>

Success story number

4

Success Story Name

Learning-p2i: Miller International Knowledge

Success story description

Online learning environment "Learning-p2i" which includes FAIR data management and research integrity within open science, with special courses on FAIRification.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://learning-p2i.eu/>

Additional Activity category

6. Contribution to the development of new standards, regulations and policies

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities that aim at the development of new standards and regulations and new public policy in the area of the new product/innovation and that will help in entering the innovation into the market and/or enhance its societal

uptake.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

29 762 614 €

Additional Activity Number	Additional Activity Name
6.1	Standardisation and certification activities

Additional Activity type

Standardisation and certification activities related to EOSC trusted repositories (e.g. CoreTrustSeal and FAIR)

Description of Additional Activity

1. Preparation of repositories and national repository platform for CTS certification
2. Core Trust Seal certification of institutional research data repositories and local storages connected to DORIS repository work
3. CESSDA Trust support and AUSSDA CTS certification
4. Support for CoreTrustSeal (re-)certification
5. Maintenance of certification services related to Core Trust Seal
6. Financial contribution to the board and secretariat of Core Trust Seal
7. Certification activities of internal ORD working groups
8. Accreditation to IODE Quality Management Framework
9. Investment in repository certifications stimulate the awareness and skill-levels for how to make data FAIR and help increase the volume of FAIR language data collections
10. Validator RECOLECTA (National validator) for open access repositories
11. Application of FAIR principles and Core Trust Seal certification (RDA & WDS) for Data Centers and services of the Ocean and Solid Earth Data Centre

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
OO12 Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

6 078 141 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

CoreTrustSeal: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) - Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)

Success story description

DANS is founding father of CoreTrustSeal and long-time contributor to Board, secretariat and assembly of reviewers.
CoreTrustSeal offers to any interested data repository a core level certification based on the Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements. This universal catalogue of requirements reflects the core characteristics of trustworthy data repositories.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia

Website

<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

Research Institutes
 Public Authorities
 Public at large
 Other

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

RECOLECTA: Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology

Success story description

Validator RECOLECTA (National validator) for open access repositories. RECOLECTA, or Collector of Open Science, is the national aggregator of open access repositories. All Spanish digital infrastructures in which research results are published and / or deposited in open access are grouped together on this platform.

Audience or target group

Industry
 Research Institutes
 Public at large
 Academia
 Public Authorities
 Other

Website

www.recolecta.fecyt.es

Additional Activity Number

6.2

Additional Activity Name

Translate FAIR guidelines and frameworks

Additional Activity type

Translate FAIR guidelines and frameworks to make them applicable to other digital objects, such as software, code, data management plans, protocols

Description of Additional Activity

1. Development of applicable FAIR guidelines and frameworks
2. Establishment of templates and protocols to manage data according to FAIR principles for the research community
3. Contribution to the development of applicable FAIR guidelines and DMP elaboration guidelines through EERTIS
4. Implementation of discipline specific RDM strategies
5. Implementation of a data management policy together with DMPs
6. Work on FAIR Research Objects and FAIR ontologies
7. Development of Metadata for Machines tools
8. Participation in RDA, IVOA, IHDEA, IPDA working groups
9. Involvement in EOSC Association's Task Forces work
10. Contribution to the translation of FAIR guidelines into specific software, code and other research products

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
- SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
- OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
- OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025
- OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public

Amount per activity

7 231 563 €

Private

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN): Fonds Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Vlaanderen (Research Foundation Flanders)

Success story description

This development work is done for Flanders by the Expertise Centre for Research and Development (ECOOM), on behalf of the Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB)/Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN). The coordination hub of this board is handled by FWO. Work is also done within the Flemish Research Information Space (FRIS).

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

www.frdn.be

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

FAIR Research Objects and FAIR ontologies: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Success story description

Work on FAIR Research Objects and FAIR ontologies.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

https://foops.linkeddata.es/foops

Additional Activity Number

6.3

Additional Activity Name

Standardisation of PID resource

Additional Activity type

Continuous standardisation of PID resource types and promotion of new practices to expand the range of identifiable research objects e.g. instruments, services, organisations and software

Description of Additional Activity

1. Collaboration with DataCite with respect to various PID standardization activities, work with DataCite DOI service
2. Alignment of PID usage across national DOI users
3. Using and promoting the use of DOI for OGS digital materials
4. Application in institutional context (eRA, PID service), contributions to committees (e.g., DataCite, CrossRef, ORCID-DE, Eurocris)
5. Setting up a national PID roadmaps
6. Integration of ORCID, DOI and other PID in universities' system
7. PID management, nation-wide services DOI-Service, ORCID, activities in the RDA National PID Strategies Working Group
8. Support communities in the standardization of PID resource types
9. Involvement in EOSC Association's Task Forces work (EOSC Task Force PID policy and implementation)
10. Establishment of the National Centre for PIDs (ISSN, ORCID consortium, DataCite consortium, ROR) that will provide methodological and financial support to RPOs and funders to implement persistent identifiers to their workflows and systems
11. Contribution to the documents on PID technical architecture that aim to identify opportunities for how interoperability between PID services can be achieved within the framework of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
12. Costs related to PIDs licensing (DataCite, Handle, CrossRef, ORCID)
13. PID analysis project within Knowledge Exchange Centre

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
 SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
 SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
 OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025
 OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
 OO11 Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

5 846 126 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

PID roadmap: Coöperatie SURF u.a

Success story description

In the area of PIDs a working group is currently setting up a national PID roadmap, This is inspired by other countries (UK, Australia, Finland) and the recently published PID roadmap that the Dutch national funder NWO has developed.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://www.surf.nl/en/national-roadmap-for-persistent-identifiers>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

DOI for OGS: Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale

Success story description

The National Oceanographic Data Centre, at OGS, manages the most comprehensive marine data archive in Italy. Using and promoting the use of DOI for OGS digital materials. The OGS institutional repository for research products is providing a handle for each resource stored.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://nodc.ogs.it/catalogs/doi>

Additional Activity Number

6.4

Additional Activity Name

Domain-specific standards and Metadata

Additional Activity type

Support all research communities to develop and adopt domain-specific standards and to consolidate common metadata and data schema for use in the EOSC context

Description of Additional Activity

1. Support research communities in the SSH and beyond to adopt domain-specific standards
2. Working with research communities through national Task Forces to support their adoption of the metadata standards relevant in their domains
3. Support to LifeWatch and CSIC's Teledetection Thematic Platform on the adoption of relevant standards for their domains of knowledge and FAIR principles
4. Support French astronomy community for the development and adoption of astronomy community standards (IVOA)

5. Development and adoption of domain-specific standards with CyVerse Austria
6. Work with the optical microscopy and electronic microscopy scientific communities to implement interoperable data archive and analysis services, support for adopting metadata and file format standards to ease data access and discovery
7. Support communities - within and beyond ICT research domains – in transferring knowledge and consolidating common metadata
8. Contribution to development and adoption of data/metadata standards in BSC research domains
9. Contribution to the development of institutional and national health data interoperability guidelines (HealthyCloud, BY-COVID)
10. Setting up the Expert Methodology Unit that serves as a primary point of consultation for the Czech R&D&I community in research metadata management with the aim to define general metadata schema recommendations and develop and/or adopt domain-specific standards
11. Expert activities within ISO Technical Committee with a focus on Registry and Terminology Standards (Geoinformatics)
12. Support disciplinary communities in NFDI projects (Text+, NFDI4Culture)
13. Support arts and humanities research communities in developing/adopting new standards, development of EPIDOC encoding language for ancient sources
14. The Digital Humanities Advanced Research Centre supports domain specific development of ontologies for semantic web applications
15. Facilitate the creation of common data schema for use in the EOSC context
16. Metadata librarian and domain specific research support staff to support researchers with the adoption and implementation of domain specific standards

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
- OO12 Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

10 606 784 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

RDM: Universität Wien (University of Vienna)

Success story description

RDM support for the social sciences in Austria. RDM support for the humanities and the life sciences at the University of Vienna.

AUSSDA is a consortium consisting of the Universities of Vienna, Graz, Linz, Innsbruck, Krems and the OeAW (Austrian Academy of Sciences). A user advisory board as well as a steering board support AUSSDA in their activities. AUSSDA also serves as the Austrian representative on the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
- Research Public
- Institutes Authorities
- Public at Other
- large

Website

<https://aussda.at>

Additional Activity category

7. Supporting ecosystem development

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities that aim at further developing and integrating the R&I ecosystem in the partnership's area - for example, knowledge sharing with technology clusters, innovation hubs, networking structures and other R&I bodies, cross-partnership cooperation.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

56 426 423 €

Additional Activity Number Additional Activity Name

7.1 Financing models

Additional Activity type

Define and test financing models for a lasting long-term EOSC sustainability framework

Description of Additional Activity

1. Participation in EOSC-A Task Force 'Long term data preservation'
2. Contribution to the work of EOSC Association Financial Sustainability Task Force

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users
OO14 Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 323 500 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Additional Activity Number Additional Activity Name

7.2 Development of consensual EOSC frameworks and guidelines

Additional Activity type

Development of consensual EOSC frameworks and guidelines (e.g. for interoperability, AAI, the implementation of EOSC rules of participation)

Description of Additional Activity

1. Participation in EOSC-A Advisory Group 'Technical challenges on EOSC' – Task Force 'AAI Architecture', Task Force 'Technical interoperability of data and services'
2. Work on EOSC compatible AAI ecosystem for specific scientific domains
3. Contribution to AAI standards and best practices definition from the HPC centre and related services operator perspective
4. Improve of usability via elaborating the access control and interoperable authentication among different standards
5. Participation in the EOSC Association's Task Forces: Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring, Long-Term Data Preservation

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes

Funding sources

Amount per activity

2 847 854 €

No

Public
 Private

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

National guidelines on Open Science: Linnaeus University

Success story description

Through the University's participation in SUHF national initiatives towards these guidelines. Contributing to national guidelines on open science developed by Swedish National Library (KB). The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions was founded in 1995 as an organisation for institutional cooperation on a voluntary basis. 38 universities and university colleges in Sweden are members (16 universities, 18 university colleges and 4 university art colleges).

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://suhf.se/in-english/>

Additional Activity Number

7.3

Additional Activity Name

Support to knowledge building and sharing with the research domains to support data-intensive-science and inter-disciplinary research

Additional Activity type

Through the University's participation in SUHF national initiatives towards these guidelines. Contributing to national guidelines on open science developed by Swedish National Library (KB).

Description of Additional Activity

1. Collaboration with national RPOs and researcher networks to facilitate transition towards Open Science (FAIR Data, RDM)
2. Coordination and support across all CSIC research areas with regards to digital and open science through CSIC's Digital Science thematic platform
3. Dedicated domain experts in the Swedish National Data Service network that serve as a support in knowledge building and sharing
4. Setting up synergistic research support in all areas of research data management and facilitating a transition to Open Science
5. Dedicated staff to support researchers with interdisciplinary data interoperability across department and projects
6. Various knowledge sharing activities towards engagement of research communities in open science practice
7. Establishment of Digital Competence Centers with a focus on improving research data management practices and the adoption of FAIR and Open Science
8. Data Access Unit for Swedish National Data Service Biodiversity data through ArtDatabanken, NAIS, UPPMAX/Bianca and VESTA/capacity building for sensitive data
9. Organisation and engagement of the EOSC network in Poland and knowledge building in the EOSC ecosystem in Poland across domains
10. The ICDI CC provides a support to researchers and research communities through dedicated events and meetings to share know-how and knowledge
11. Establishment of a curation and community building team for the ORKG, working on onboarding users on the ORKG and related EOSC services
12. The cost of personnel of Research Data/ Research Data Management offices
13. Metadata librarian and domain specific research support staff to support researchers with interdisciplinary data interoperability across department and projects

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

11 473 283 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

ArtDatabanken: Uppsala University

Success story description

Data Access Unit for Swedish National Data Service Biodiversity data through ArtDatabanken, NAISS, UPPMAX/Bianca and VESTA/capacity building for sensitive data.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

www.artdatabanken.se

Additional Activity Number

7.4

Additional Activity Name

Industry-academia cooperation

Additional Activity type

Building industry-academia cooperation (e.g. GAIA-X and other industry-driven initiatives)

Description of Additional Activity

1. Collaboration Sunet/RISE to establish a joint national EuroHPC node, focusing on industry-academic use cases
2. Foster collaboration with industry stakeholders within GAIA-X through CSIC's Digital Science thematic platform
3. Involvement in GAIA-X AISBL, GAIA-X national hubs, EuroHPC, Digital Innovation Hubs and other efforts which support collaboration with industry and their implementation on regional and national level
4. Establishment of Romanian National Competence Center (RoNCC) in the field of HPC that aims to create a network of competencies in HPC, coordination of National Competence Center for HPC activities
5. Setting up an own Open Desk that offers any company the possibility of submitting its innovation needs that can be solved by Modelling Simulation and Optimization technologies in a Data rich Environment (MSO-DE). It is devoted to coordinate and facilitate the necessary exchanges in the field of application-driven mathematical research and its exploitation for innovations in industry, science, and society.
6. Building industry - academia cooperation within Virtual Center for Digital Science and Innovation
7. Facilitate the use of HPC / HPDA / AI applications by different users, also from academia, industry, and public administration
8. Promotion of industry-academia cooperation at regional and national level within DIH4CAT and EuroCC Spain
9. Implementation of a GAIA-X compliant data space for sustainable manufacturing

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

7 395 548 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Success story description

INFN is a founding member of the Gaia-X initiative. The aim of the Gaia-X Hub Italia Association is to promote the data ecosystem in Italy. The Hub will represent the reference point for Italian companies interested in developing data-enhancement projects, following principles such as interoperability, privacy, and control of proprietary data. The Hub is also a point of connection with Gaia-X's national counterparts at European level, to develop a federated, sovereign and fully operational continental data ecosystem. Within the ICSC National Center; partnerships and competitive innovation grants between INFN and industries have been defined to foster technology scale-up and transfer; support new start-ups and spin-offs; address skill gaps; promote entrepreneurial culture.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Academia
- Research Institutes
- Public Authorities
- Public at large
- Other

Website

<https://www.gaiax-italia.eu/>

Additional Activity Number

7.5

Additional Activity Name

Persistent Identifier (PID) policy and architecture

Additional Activity type

enforcement and implementation of the EOSC Persistent Identifier (PID) policy and architecture

Description of Additional Activity

1. Enforcement and implementation of EOSC PID policy through (revised) institutional/ national Open Science policies/ documents
2. Implementation of automatic DOIs in datasets collected in one beamline supporting ICAT data Catalogue
3. Support communities in adoption of metadata schemas related and required by the PIDs providers by the National Centre for PIDs
4. Support of ORCID, DOI and other PID systems via institutional infrastructure and support (eRA)
5. Enforcement of institutional policy to promote the adoption and use of ORCID among researchers
6. Implementation & maintenance of pilot PID services for Italian User community

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
- OO11 Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

2 802 791 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

PTCRIS programme: Foundation for Science and Technology

Success story description

This caption includes the effort to ensure compliance with PTCRIS programme. This programme aims to facilitate the production, access, sharing and management of information on national scientific activity, It is responsible for developing a regulatory framework and infrastructures to create an integrated ecosystem of information on science in Portugal.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Academia
- Research Institutes
- Public Authorities
- Public at large
- Other

Website

<https://ptcris.pt/>

large

Additional Activity Number **Additional Activity Name**
7.6 European infrastructure

Additional Activity type

Encouraging and incentivising use of European infrastructure for sharing of research software

Description of Additional Activity

1. Promotion of the use of Software Heritage and FAIR software route
2. Fostering usage of EOSC across all CSIC institutes through CSIC's Digital Science thematic platform
3. Promotion of the services from ERICs like EATRIS and ELIXIR through the institutional newsletter
4. HPCQS platform design activities
5. Implementation and expansion of MeHeart open-source optimized model of solid mechanics of the myocardium to reproduce the cardiac electro-mechanics in HPC environment for industrial, clinical, and academic applications

Link to partnership general objectives

GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO6 Provide an increased number of services and resources to ensure that European research is discovered and reused within and across disciplines to extract new knowledge
SO7 EOSC is operationalised and provides a stable and valuable infrastructure supporting researchers addressing societal challenges
OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

3 287 570 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

CSIC's Digital Science Thematic Platform: Consejo Superior de investigaciones científicas (CSIC) - Spanish National Research Council

Success story description

Fostering usage of EOSC across all CSIC institutes through CSIC's Digital Science thematic platform. We are the Digital Science and Innovation Platform. Our mission is to innovate in all areas of digital science and data lifecycle management, from planning, acquisition and processing to publication and preservation. This PTI has a clear focus on innovation in all areas that generate economic and societal impact, with special interest in health and wellbeing, agriculture, climate and secure society. This platform also aims to promote training in digital competencies to facilitate everyday tasks.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://pti-cienciadigital.csic.es/>

Additional Activity Number **Additional Activity Name**
7.7 KPIs and FAIR data

Additional Activity type

Monitoring of EOSC key performance indicators (KPI's), investments and FAIR data production and management

Description of Additional Activity

1. National mapping/monitoring on open access to research data within national assignment
2. Engagement in OpenAIRE monitoring activities
3. Monitoring closely the progress on institutional KPIs by the Open Science team
4. Support the related work of GSRI on OS and innovation monitoring
5. Contribution to national open science website by publishing an online open science dashboard with a variety of

indicators

6. Dedicated monitoring working group within the EOSC Support Office Austria

7. Contribution to monitoring work through the EOSC Steering Board

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO5 The EOSC Interoperability Framework supports an increasing range and quantity of FAIR digital objects including data, software and other research artefacts

OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)

OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025

Link to projects

Yes

No

Funding sources

Public

Private

Amount per activity

2 519 712 €

Success story

Yes

No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

KPI Survey: National Science Centre Poland

Success story description

With regard to the monitoring of the EOSC Key Performance Indicators, NCN supervises data collection on national contributions by performing an annual survey on the national contributions to EOSC. NCN also analyses and provides the survey data and is involved in the strategic discussions with the sub-group A of the EOSC SB. Moreover, NCN exemplifies investments and FAIR data production and management by requiring Data Management Plan in the NCN's project applications and final reports and sharing FAIR data for funded publications.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

https://ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/regulaminy/wytyczne_zarzadzanie_danymi_ang.pdf

Additional Activity Number

7.8

Additional Activity Name

Rewards and Recognition Framework

Additional Activity type

Contributing to a rewards and recognition framework that incentivises FAIR data and Open Science

Description of Additional Activity

1. Development of national rewards and recognition framework within national FAIR Strategy implementation
2. Establishment of Research Assessment Group dedicated following topics related to the rewards and recognition framework that incentivises FAIR data and Open Science
3. Promotion, dissemination, consultation/ mutual learning exercises and policy advise on new indicators for research assessment and rewards, including EOSC, Open Science, RDM
4. Participation in EOSC-A Advisory Group 'Research careers and curricula' – Task Force 'Research careers, recognition and credit'
5. Contribution to development a new Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF)
6. Alignment of Quality Research Framework with OS, DORA and EOSC standards and principles
7. Development of university strategy for changes in recognition and rewards, inclusion of FAIR research data and DORA into the rewards policy during 2023
8. Scientometric analyses and advisory services for university's researchers and research units
9. Contribution to the alignment of the national rewards and incentives framework to the European initiatives
10. Evaluation of new research assessment methods in line with EUs agreement on reforming research assessment
11. A pilot for responsible metrics implementation in assessments and job applications

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 927 440 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Rewards and recognition framework: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Success story description

Actions supporting the rewards and recognition framework within research infrastructure enhancement.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.mur.gov.it/it/aree-tematiche/ricerca/programma-operativo-nazionale-pon>

Additional Activity Number

7.9

Additional Activity Name

Activities contributing to strategic and operational alignment, coordination and synergies with other partnerships

Additional Activity type

Activities contributing to strategic and operational alignment, coordination and synergies with other partnerships: HE missions, initiatives, research data commons and data spaces.

Description of Additional Activity

1. Collaboration with other infrastructures, partnerships, Horizon Europe missions, to implement into the strategic and operational plans at EU level innovative pediatric research to be developed in synergy
2. Contribution to strategic and operational alignment of pan-European e-Infrastructures through activities in e-IRG and EGI
3. Participations in international research infrastructures, providing data for an OS/EOSC environment e.g ELIXIR Belgium, AnaEE-Belgium, CLARIAH-VL, DiSSCo, EMBRC, ICOS, EMPHASIS-Belgium, EUFAR
4. Participation in EOSC-A task forces
5. Coordination of national Network for e-Science, fostering the cooperation among main national stakeholders in e-Science, including Open Science
6. Contribution to national Open Research Forum which brings together stakeholders in national research ecosystem to help develop national policies on open research
7. Collaboration with/ within the European Consortia of Universities for practices exchange and better alignment of OS approaches
8. Contribution to OS committees or working groups of the Science Europe, the Guild, EUA, LIBER, RDA
9. Contribution to discussions in committees and partnerships (e.g, Alliance of German Research Organisations, NFDI, DINI)
10. Alignment with euroCRIS and EOSC
11. Collaboration with the relevant data space initiatives, such as the Language Data Space
12. Contribution to relevant EU initiatives aligned with EOSC objectives: SeaDATANET, Science Europe, GBIF, OPERAS

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
 GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
 SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
 OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Funding

Amount per activity

Yes
 No

sources 16 979 679 €

Public
 Private

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Strategic and operational alignments: Vetenskapsrådet - Swedish Research Council

Success story description

Contributions to strategic and operational alignments relating to organisation's participation in among other, programme committee, national contact point, Conosc, National Point of Reference on Scientific Information, Science Europe, ERAPermed 1+MG, Nordic Commons, 1+ million genomes.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://www.vr.se/english.html>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Language Data Space: CLARIN

Success story description

CLARIN will collaborate with the relevant data space initiatives, such as the Language Data Space. The creation of the LDS platform aims at marking a turning point in the approach to the collection of language resources: the LDS will help European industry to compete globally with the language technology services provided by US or Chinese companies, and to build trust throughout the language data sharing process.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

https://language-data-space.ec.europa.eu/about_en
#the-language-data-space

Additional Activity Number

7.11

Additional Activity Name

Contact points at national or institutional levels

Additional Activity type

Contact points at national or institutional levels and coordination mechanisms for EOSC uptake by the research communities, infrastructure connection and FAIR implementation

Description of Additional Activity

1. Coordination and promotion of collaboration on the national work on open access to research data, coordination of the national engagement in EOSC
2. Participation in the Hellenic Open Science Initiative that aims to promote EOSC at national level
3. Coordination of national activities towards the implementation of EOSC, including work on the general conditions for this implementation
4. Setting up the national EOSC secretariats
5. Coordination of OS national activities as the national contact points for EOSC, being also the OS and EOSC national helpdesks, supporting the EOSC uptake
6. Coordination of the national EOSC Forums, running EOSC national Coordination Forums
7. Coordination of the national OS Task Forces, engagement with national stakeholders, co-creation activities for potential 'EOSC-proof' services in collaboration with research organisations and researchers
8. Establishment of the institutional EOSC reference points
9. Participation in the coordination boards for implementation of the EOSC initiative at national level
10. Participating in the national governances of the EOSC
11. Alignment with the EOSC-A as the national EOSC-A Mandated Organisation
12. Contact point for EOSC for national Association of Higher Educational Institutions
13. Support and coordination of the participation of national institutions, organisations, and individual members in the Research Data Alliance Europe, linking the community to EOSC
14. Establishment of national Open Science Task Forces and/ or national EOSC Support Offices

15. Coordination of national Open Science Cloud initiatives
 16. Participation in national Open Science Observatories

Link to partnership general objectives

GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
 GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
 SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
 OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
 OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

3 869 047 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Coordination mechanisms: BELNET

Success story description

- a) Co-ordinating the Taskforce CISCFS OS - EOSC part of the Belgian governance
- b) Aligning with the EOSC-A as the Belgian Mandated Organisation (workshops, GA, AAP, symposium, etc.)
- c) Engaging with the stakeholder in the Belgian R&E community (Customer relations)
- d) Prospecting Co-creation activities for potential 'EOSC-proof' services in collaboration with research organisations and researchers
- e) Participating in the Belgian governance of the EOSC (contributing to the Belgian national EOSC coordination: CIS/CFS OS)
- f) Participating to and aligning with the Géant-A – GN4-3 & GN5 / Open Science

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://www.belspo.be/belspo/coordination/addgrp.asp?l=en&group=CFS-CIS%20Open%20Science>

Additional Activity category

8. Communication, dissemination, awareness raising, citizen engagement

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes activities in the areas of communication and dissemination, in order to ensure that citizens "take up" and accept the new product/innovation, as well as learning about user needs. It also goes further to cover activities that aim at awareness raising and stakeholder engagement in relation to the new product/innovation.

Additional activity reported under this category

- Yes
 No

Amount per category

7 698 569 €

Additional Activity Number

8.1

Additional Activity Name

EOSC-related communication, dissemination, outreach and awareness raising activities

Additional Activity type

EOSC-related communication, dissemination, outreach and awareness raising activities

Description of Additional Activity

1. EOSC-related communication and awareness raising activities through all available communication institutional channels such as webpages, magazines, newsletters and through social media
2. Organisation of national Tripartite events involving the national stakeholders
3. Running EOSC Roadshow and other national and local events that aim to promote EOSC to research communities
4. Organisation of thematic seminars to promote EOSC-related topics within the institution and towards the citizenship
5. Organisation of EOSC information events
6. Dissemination, outreach, social media postings, events, and webinars for research communities on topics including research data management, EOSC, EUDAT, FAIR data, data infrastructures and research data services
7. Creation of a dedicated space on the institutional website to explain EOSC
8. Dissemination activities related to the EOSC community through the RDM Forum event
9. Online materials on EOSC and OS disseminated among national researchers, data stewards, service providers, university authorities as well as local and national authorities
10. Articles, publications, conferences, hands-on discussions, online events for EOSC and FAIR promotion (e.g., the Open Science Café, e-Science meetings)
11. Citizen engagement through monitoring surveys with the use of innovative applications
12. Promotion of EOSC at all levels by engaging with relevant communities and stakeholders of the rare disease field
13. Participation to the activities of the recently founded “National Public Engagement Network” APENet, contributing to making a science communication ecosystem more open and inclusive
14. Engagement activities with policy makers (ministries), RPOs, research communities as well as with citizens through various projects funded by the Recovery and Resilience Plan

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the ‘new normal’

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
- SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
- SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
- OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

4 011 110 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Newsletter: Fundación Para La Investigación Biomédica Del Hospital Universitario La Paz (FIBHULP)

Success story description

Through the institutional newsletter and webpage, FIBHULP promotes EOSC among the IdiPAZ community.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

<https://www.idipaz.es/PaginaDinamica.aspx?IdPag=28&Lang=EN>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Communication: University of Coimbra

Success story description

Within this category, the institution promotes regular workshops, news, press releases, among other initiatives, in order to raise awareness and engagement with the academic communities and public at large.

Audience or target group

- Industry
- Academia
- Research Institutes
- Public Authorities
- Public at large
- Other

Website

https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/

Additional Activity Number

8.2

Additional Activity Name

Promoting EOSC

Additional Activity type

Promoting EOSC at all levels by engaging with relevant communities and stakeholders

Description of Additional Activity

1. Maintenance of the dedicated webpages presenting EOSC-related activities, addressed to various communities
2. Collaboration with the infrastructures and e-infrastructures managers
3. Regular webinars addressed to researchers where EOSC and engagement opportunities are disseminated
4. Promotion of EOSC by engaging with research communities in the SSH, with the national stakeholders and the national infrastructures
5. Poli-social Award - the initiative provides funding to research projects with high social impact according to the paradigm of citizen science (the selected projects are evaluated also according to EOSC-related parameters)
6. Promotion of EOSC within Digital Innovation Hub, managed by the EOSC Support Office Austria
7. Management of large platform called BrainMap - the online community of researchers, innovators, technicians, and entrepreneurs with more than 50.000 accounts or EERIS platform that offers an overview of existing research facilities, equipment, services, and technological services at national level
8. Management and content provision for the EOSC PL website
9. Promotion of EOSC in various activities, sometimes in close cooperation with OpenAIRE
10. Collaboration with national funders, research performing organisations, policymakers, and research communities
11. Promotion of EOSC via Cluster Forschungsdaten activities
12. Engagement with arts and humanities research communities at national or institutional level (raising awareness. promoting EOSC. etc.)
13. Leverage of existing network and communication channels to general e-infrastructure users' community
14. Promotion of Open Science with national events, press releases, posts on social media, web news on institutional web sites, paper material (leaflets, roll up, posters), contents on the dedicated section of the institutional web portal
15. Organisation of meetings with all national based members of EOSC-A Task Forces
16. Engagement activities through EOSC Board and membership fee

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
- SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
- SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
- SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
- OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO5 Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing)
- OO7 Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan- European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025
- OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
- OO9 Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership
- OO14 Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

3 687 459 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Innovation National Supercomputing Center: Technical University of Ostrava

Success story description

Leveraging existing network and communication channels to HPC users community.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

www.it4i.cz

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Engagement: Consortium GARR Association (Gestione Ampliamento Rete Ricerca)

Success story description

ICDI (Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure) is a forum created by representatives of major Italian Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures, with the aim of promoting synergies at the national level, and optimising the Italian participation to European and global challenges in this field, including the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the European Data Infrastructure (EDI) and HPC. ICDI have carried out engagement activities with policy makers (ministries), research performing organisations and research communities as well as with citizens.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.icdi.it/en/>

Additional Activity category

9. Other

Definition of Additional Activity category

This category includes any other activities that cannot be included in the above categories

Additional activity reported under this category

Yes
 No

Amount per category

19 067 736 €

Additional Activity Number

9.1

Additional Activity Name

Introduction of EOSC-specific references in research programmes and EOSC-related criteria for R&I funding

Additional Activity type

Introduction of EOSC-specific references in research programmes and EOSC-related criteria for R&I funding

Description of Additional Activity

1. Establishment of the requirements for open access to publications of funded research
2. Setting up the requirements that a data management plan is drawn up before the research starts and that the plan is maintained and complied with
3. Drafting specific requirements for funded infrastructures to provide research data and software as open as possible and as soon as possible
4. Introduction of EOSC-specific references in all relevant nationally funded projects
5. Providing input to the Ministry for the set-up of new calls to support Open Science, also providing input to the definition of conditions like mandatory use of DMPs in general research calls
6. Support in drafting OS related criteria in different funding streams
7. Collaboration with the Ministry and other funders on adoption of Open Science requirements in the funded projects
8. Provision of the additional funding for Open Science activities in research projects in all funding schemes that can be spent on any activities that will support sharing of research artefacts generated in the project (costs of open access publications, sharing the data in line with FAIR principles, salaries of data stewards, maintenance of institutional Open Science infrastructure)

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

4 428 408 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Additional Funding OS Activities: National Science Centre

Success story description

In order to support Open Science best practice among researchers, NCN provides an additional funding for Open Science activities in research projects in all funding schemes. The additional funding amounts to 2% of the project's direct costs. The Open Science fund can be spent on any activities that will support sharing of research artefacts generated in the project (costs of open access publications, sharing the data in line with FAIR principles, salaries of data stewards, maintenance of institutional Open Science infrastructure. It also includes the validation of NCN grant application as for the dissemination of the research outputs in Open Access.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.ncn.gov.pl/en/fina nsowanie-nauki/otwarta-nauka>

Additional Activity Number

9.2

Additional Activity Name

Support for open access publication

Additional Activity type

Activities in support of open publishing and initiatives to promote wider open access publication through the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

1. Support through Figshare Bolin centre and Figshare - an online open access repository to preserve and share research outputs, including figures, datasets, images, and videos
2. Open access publishing-related activities carried out by dedicated teams/ staff e.g., Open Access Office
3. Support to publication in Diamond Open Access through the institutional e-publishing Editorial Service
4. Creation of the Open Access Award to encourage the engagement of university staff in developing and promoting open research including open access publishing or in making publications freely accessible
5. Open access publishing activity within institutional DSpace repository
6. Financial support for activities to move to open and FAIR publishing within the EMS Publishing House
7. Offering institutional standard services for Open Access Publishing (ORFEO)
8. Internalisation of the Polish monographs via Open Edition Books that promotes Open Access publishing and sustainability model
9. Support Open Science organisations like SCOSS, participation in OpenAIRE, institutional contributions to European scholarly communication and publication infrastructures (e.g., OPERAS, OAPEN, DOAJ)
10. Activities of the University Library Centre and fundings to support open access publications
11. Press and advisory services for open access publishing at the universities
12. Support of Green, Gold and Diamond open access
13. Publication funds and transformatory agreements
14. Monitoring and update of the university's Open Access policy
15. Support OA through BOARD – Bicocca Open Archive Research Data - platform: open access institutional research data management system for managing, publishing, disseminating, and storing the data
16. Operation of the institutional open access repository for publications and research data in a EOSC compatible framework
17. Contribution to the ChronosHub - an Open Access management platform

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
 SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
 SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain- specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
 OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership

Link to projects

Yes
 No

Funding sources

Public
 Private

Amount per activity

9 713 128 €

Success story

Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Open Science at Lund University

Success story description

The main purpose of the project Open Science at Lund University is to set up an Open Science organization at Lund University to implement policies and communication strategies, develop support and infrastructures regarding citizen science, FAIR data and open source.

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://www.lunduniversity.lu.se>

Success story number

2

Success Story Name

Open Access Fund: Fonds National de la Recherche Luxembourg

Success story description

The aim of the Open Access Fund is to promote the free access to research results from FNR-(co)funded projects.
 The programme provides financial support to cover article processing charges that may arise through the publication of peer-reviewed research results in Open Access.
 To simplify the processes related to the FNR Open Access Policies and Open Access funding, the FNR has partnered with ChronosHub, an Open Access management platform. This collaboration facilitates the compliancy check with the FNR Open Access Policies and the direct payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs) for authors and institutions

Audience or target group

Industry Academia
 Research Public
 Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
 large

Website

<https://www.fnr.lu/funding-instruments/open-access-fund/>

Additional Activity Number

9.3

Additional Activity Name

National or institutional strategies

Additional Activity type

Adoption of national or institutional strategies for digital transformation and related roadmaps including a reference to the EOSC

Description of Additional Activity

1. Support to the implementation of the Digital Strategy priorities
2. Implementation of the national digital transformation strategies
3. Adoption of the national strategy for FAIR research data management
4. Implementation of the institutional strategies for digital transformation and related roadmaps through a dedicated

working group

5. Contribution to the national AI strategy and actions in the field of data platforms
6. Adoption of the national strategy for digital transformation
7. Contribution to the digital transformation across the Catalan region
8. Contribution to the national Roadmap for Digital Transformation which also includes actions for Open Science and EOSC
9. Digitalisation of the cultural heritage collections within the national program
10. Research Data Management policy and Roadmap implementation
11. Activities within the Digital University Hub - the cooperation and service platform for digital and social transformation initiatives by Austrian universities

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO1 Increase in the number of relevant research results that are made available as open as possible by researchers performing publicly funded research
SO2 Professional data stewards are increasingly available in research performing organisations in Europe to support Open Science
SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design
SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science
OO1 Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025
OO2 Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023)
OO3 Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership
OO4 Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO6 Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership
OO8 Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership
OO13 Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 176 453 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

National AI strategy: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas

Success story description

Participation in projects aligned with the National AI strategy and actions in the field of data platforms. Promoting digital enabling technologies such as connectivity infrastructures or massive data environments to facilitate data sharing. Developing advanced data management and analysis capabilities linked to strategic Supercomputing infrastructures (HPC).

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Institutes Public Authorities
 Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/presidente/actividades/Documents/2020/ENIAResumen2B.pdf>

Additional Activity Number

9.4

Additional Activity Name

New policies on Open Science

Additional Activity type

Adoption of new policies on Open Science referring to the use of the EOSC or the implementation of the FAIR principles. Definition of policy targets and action plans for the implementation of those policies

Description of Additional Activity

1. Publication of the institutional policies on management and sharing of data
2. Revision and update of the institutional policies on open access to publications
3. Adoption of the institutional road maps to Open Science with a set of the recommendations
4. Support to the implementation of activities included in the proposal for a National Open Science Plan
5. Implementation of the national policies on Open Science
6. Adoption of the national Open Science Strategies and Roadmaps, e.g., roadmap for the implementation of open science in Ukraine until 2030
7. Contribution to the development of the strategic framework for OS at national level
8. Implementation of the Slovak National Strategy for Open Science 2021-2028 that aims to improve the availability of the Slovak scientific results and change the system of the research and evaluation processes towards better transparency, reproducibility, and integrity
9. Implementation of the Swedish Policy on Open Science, Roadmap and Guide Open Science and University Open Science Policy
10. Adoption and harmonisation of the national policies on open access and FAIR data with universities' policies
11. Support of the academic and research community regarding the implementation of Open Science policies
12. Contribution to the activities in the National Programme Open Science (NPOS)
13. Adoption of the Swedish National Research Data Framework for Open Science
14. Establishment of the university policy on open research data in 2023 and implementation of the institutional plan for prioritised actions in support of Open Science
15. Drafting the Polish National Open Data Policy with a consultancy role of the Open Data Advisory Group
16. Publication of the CERN's Open Science policy with reference to EOSC
17. Implementation of institutional Open Access policy for mandatory deposit of publications in institutional repository (OpenDOAR compliant)
18. Roll-out of the institutional updated open science and publication policy
19. Adoption of the FNR Open Access Policies
20. Implementation of the Flemish Open Science Board roadmap

Link to partnership general objectives

GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Link to partnership specific objectives

SO3 Development and adoption of incentives for researchers to perform Open Science
SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design

Link to projects

- Yes
 No

Funding sources

- Public
 Private

Amount per activity

2 300 421 €

Success story

- Yes
 No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

National and Institutional policies: Stockholm University

Success story description

Upcoming work with national policy Open Science Implementation work locally
Work Roadmap and Guide Open Science and University Open Science Policy

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
 Research Public
Institutes Authorities
 Public at Other
large

Website

www.suhf.se

Additional Activity Number

9.5

Additional Activity Name

Global cooperation for Open Science

Additional Activity type

Liaise internationally to develop a global cooperation framework for Open Science infrastructures

Description of Additional Activity

1. Collaboration with the Federated Institutional Repositories of Scientific Publications Network which is a Latin American network of open access repositories

2. Collaboration aimed at raising the awareness for the potential benefits of sharing language resources via active links with nodes in South Africa, the US, Australia, and Latin America
3. Liaise with regional networks around the world (Canada, Latin America, UN, GOSC, RDA, COAR) which include technology transfer, know-how and practices

Link to partnership general objectives

- GO1 Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- GO2 Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- GO3 Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

Link to partnership specific objectives

- SO8 Essential additional functionalities for end users from the public and private sectors are implemented in EOSC (these developments are complementary to those of other European data spaces)
- SO9 EOSC increasingly establishes ties with related initiatives from regions around the world and becomes a partner in global cooperation frameworks for Open Science

Link to projects

- Yes
- No

Funding sources

- Public
- Private

Amount per activity

449 326 €

Success story

- Yes
- No

Success story number

1

Success Story Name

Knowledge-Exchange and RDA: CSC - IT Center for Science Ltd

Success story description

The Knowledge Exchange (KE) partners are six key national organisations within Europe tasked with developing infrastructure and services to enable the use of digital technologies to improve higher education and research: CSC in Finland, CNRS in France, DeiC in Denmark, DFG in Germany, Jisc in the UK and SURF in the Netherlands. <https://www.knowledge-exchange.info/>

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and re-use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society.

Audience or target group

- Industry Academia
- Research Institutes Public Authorities
- Public at large Other

Website

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>